

CONTINUOUS MONITORING OF FATIGUE DEGRADATION
IN COMPOSITES BY DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

by

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The work reported in this paper draws on two continuing aspects of work on the assessment of degradation in fibre reinforced composites and on their behaviour in fatigue. It is shown that capture and analysis of the stress-strain hysteresis loop throughout the test allows the specimen condition to be monitored in real-time during a fatigue test. The recorded data are shown to correlate well with direct optical measurements of damage with a linear relationship. The uses of data can include assessing the damage within a specimen, predicting the residual life and in its absolute value as relevant to dynamic loading design applications such as springs.

INTRODUCTION

In (1-3) a normalisation procedure was developed for fatigue test data which aimed to produce a framework for assessing the numerous permutations material and lay-out available in composite materials. It was shown that data obtained under a range of tests conditions could be normalised by the ultimate strength of identical specimens measured at the fatigue test loading rate to yield a single S-N curve. The procedure was shown to be usable for tests at different frequencies (0.002 to 50 Hz), at different temperatures (- 150 °C to + 150 °C), for specimens with notches and holes, and for specimens tested after different water pre-treatments. The single normalised S-N curve obtained for the glass fibre fabric/epoxy laminate tested suggested a common mode of degradation once initial differences in the starting strength had been eliminated. Hence, it is of interest to follow the breakdown of specimens in detail throughout the fatigue test in order to investigate the failure mechanisms for this unique S-N curve.

In (4) it was shown that both stress wave (acoustic) emission and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) data could monitor degradation in GRP materials. For the latter technique it was possible to obtain a straight line relationship between the modulus and damping data and the area of

cracking for incrementally loaded tensile specimens. In these tests the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ crossply specimen was removed after each increment of ramp loading, the area of cracking measured and the dynamic measurements made using specialist DMA equipment. Similar experiments were reported in (5) using a separate dynamic mechanical excitation without removing the specimen. No direct correlation with damage was given.

These measurements would be ideal for monitoring specimens during fatigue loading where microdamage can occur at low fractions of the total specimen life and throughout the stressed volume. However, it was not acceptable to remove the specimen during the test and techniques for continuous monitoring the sample in-situ were required. Potential techniques include stress wave (acoustic) emission, radiography, thermographic monitoring, microscope observations, ultrasonic pulse transmissions, and DMA measurements. Several of these techniques are being used but in this paper attention is concentrated on the DMA technique.

To develop confidence in the technique it is necessary to conduct the same type of correlation experiment reported in (4), that is, to undertake tests on commercial materials in which it is possible to use a second direct method to confirm the source of the changes in the DMA data. In these cases it is necessary to understand the failure mode(s) present, for example, tensile fatigue of a high quality $\pm 45^\circ$ crossplied glassfibre/epoxy laminate fails initially by multiple resin/interface fracture on 45° degree planes. These cracks are easily observed visually. In this paper the hardware and software used for the DMA measurements are described together with correlation experiments using the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate.

Figure 1 Time dependence of the stress and strain response during sinusoidal loading.

Figure 2 Cross-plot of stress and strain waveform to give hysteresis loop.

DESCRIPTION OF THE MONITORING SYSTEMDerivation of dynamic modulus and damping factor

When a linear viscoelastic material is subjected to a sinusoidal displacement under steady state conditions there exists between the applied stress (σ) and the strain (ϵ) response of the same frequency a phase lag δ as shown in Figure 1.

The loss factor d for a linear viscoelastic material, alternately known as the damping factor, is given by:-

$$d = \tan \delta = E''/E' \quad (7)$$

where E' is known as the storage modulus and is proportional to the peak energy stored per cycle. $= \sigma_0/\epsilon_0 \cos \delta$

E'' is known as the loss modulus and is proportional to the net energy dissipated per cycle. $= \sigma_0/\epsilon_0 \sin \delta$

The computer analysis calculates the damping factor d from one full stress and strain cycle by determining the ratio of the dissipated energy (equal to the area within the hysteresis loop) to the stored energy (equal to the area of the enclosing rectangle). The value of δ can then be obtained from the calculated damping factor. This method has two advantages compared to measuring δ directly at the zero-crossing point to obtain d . Firstly a thousand data points are used for greater accuracy. Secondly, if non-linear behaviour is exhibited the value of the damping factor obtained is correct and it can be used to derive an apparent phase angle for the equivalent energy within the true elliptical shaped hysteresis loop for a linear material. This is because in the nonlinear case the strain response to an applied sinusoidal stress is a distorted sinusoid. Therefore the phase lag between the stress and strain waveforms varies throughout the cycle giving a distorted hysteresis loop and a damping value determined from a single measurement of the phase lag would be incorrect. In the tests reported here the hysteresis loops were not severely distorted. Further details of dynamic mechanical techniques are given in (4) and (6).

In (4) it was shown for a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ crossply that both d and E' varied linearly with crack area but had different dependencies depending on the exact fractions of 0° and 90° layers. To eliminate this difference it was necessary to crossplot the crack area against the energy dissipation per cycle which is proportional to $E_D (d_E^D - d_E^U) = E \Delta d$; where E_D is the current damaged modulus and Δd is the change in damping (ie damping of damaged specimen d_E^D - damping of undamaged specimen d_E^U). Figure 3 shows the results given in Figure 12 of (4) for a torsion pendulum test on two specimens which yielded a single dependence.

Data acquisition hardware

The data acquisition system consists of a desktop microcomputer (HP 9845) interfaced with a multiprogrammer (HP 6942A) configured for use as a twin channel high speed analogue to digital converter and memory. The multiprogrammer employs two 12 bit analogue/digital converter cards to read the ± 10 volts output from the test machine. One card is used to capture 1000 data points for each of the corresponding load and strain waveforms. The acquisition rate of the converter cards is set by the computer program from the test frequency.

Figure 3 Dependence of $G_D \Delta d_G$ upon crack area for a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate

Data acquisition software

The program requires initial inputs for the specimen dimensions, load cell and strain gauge calibrations, and test frequency. The program initiates the capture of the first set of data which are then cross-plotted to produce a stress-strain hysteresis loop for that loading cycle. The program then calculates the damping factor (d) and storage modulus (E'). The complete hysteresis loop is stored on a hard disc for subsequent re-plotting. The computer outputs to the monitor and the printer the duration of the tests, number of cycles, minimum and maximum stresses and strains, and the calculated d and E' values.

A further loop is then captured, processed and the derived data compared with the data from the previously stored loop. If the new data do not differ by more than a level of significance set by the operator from the previous result the data are used to update the monitor only and then discarded. Further monitoring cycles are then undertaken until a significant change in either the damping or the storage modulus is detected. This procedure limits the amount of data output and stored, while retaining sensitivity to significant changes in the specimen condition. Normally the sensitivity level is set to produce 20 to 30 significant data points for each fatigue test.

Throughout the test the last hysteresis loop or the trend in the data (as a function of cycles) can be displayed and/or plotted. When the specimen fails the failure is detected by the computer and the trend of the

data for the complete test can be plotted. A recent addition is the ability to plot all, or selected, of the stored hysteresis loops.

The derived data d and E' are also available as outputs from the HP computer to be fed into a stress wave emission (SWE) system. This allows direct correlations with SWE data to further extend the assessment and validation of damage monitoring methods.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The tests were undertaken on a 1251 series Instron servo-hydraulic test machine using load control with a sinusoidal waveform. A $\pm 10\%$, 25 mm gauge length clip-gauge was used for strain measurement throughout the test. The specimen was held in hydraulic grips and illuminated by two light sources angled to illuminate the damage occurring.

Tests on several materials (ie woven fabric, $0^\circ/90^\circ$ crossplies and $\pm 45^\circ$ crossplies) were assessed for their suitability for the correlation tests. The $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate was chosen as it provided both changes in the d and E' data, as well as damage that could be assessed visually.

Dumbell specimens, with the fibre angles at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the axis, were cut from a 2 m x 1 m sheet of 6 mm thick $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate (Permal (Gloucester) Ltd - XE6 material). The laminate was produced by the pre-preg and hot-press method and had a consistent structure with a very low void content. The damage occurring within the gauge length was assessed continuously throughout the test by counting the cracks formed within the gauge length. The specimens were tested at 5 Hz for stresses of 60 to 70 MPa using a R ratio of 0.1. These conditions were selected to give a reasonable duration (ie 0.5 to 3 hrs) for the visual crack observations.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Type and location of damage

The specimens consisted of 11 plies of unidirectional glassfibre/epoxy material alternately orientated $\pm 45^\circ$, of even layer thickness apart from a central layer approximately 10% thicker.

The initial onset of resin cracking occurred parallel with the 45° orientated fibres in the surface layers. Further damage occurred unevenly throughout the gauge length; each crack propagating within a layer and running across the whole width and depth of each transverse layer before being stabilised by the alternately orientated layers. Because of the consistency of the crack length and width the number of cracks recorded at each stage throughout the test can be equated approximately to the crack area. Figure 4 shows the 45° cracking in a typical specimen.

Final catastrophic failure occurred by a tensile fracture of the central layer followed by delamination of surface layers and splitting of the remaining layers.

Figure 4 Typical cracked sample showing cracks at 45° to specimen axis

Figure 5 Hysteresis loop captured during fatigue of a $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen

Dynamic mechanical data

A typical hysteresis loop at 8,986 cycles is shown in Figure 5. A full print-out for a test is given in Figure 6. The currently used print-out has been modified and the acceptance of significant data during the 'incubation' period up to 20,000 cycles has been improved. The derived d and E' data from this print-out are shown in the standard plot in Figure 7.

CONTINUOUS MONITORED FATIGUE DATA

Test 4		Frequency 5 Hz				
Specimen XE6		Max stress 62.8 MN/m ²				
		Min stress 6.4 MN/m ²				
Time	N cycles	Damping	Storage	Min. Strain	Max. Strain	
Hrs, mins		Factor	Modulus	%	%	
			GN/m ²			
0 0	0					
0 2	671	.0501	19.81	.064	.342	
0 4	1323	.0467	19.86	.070	.348	
0 21	6523	.0517	19.85	.064	.338	
0 23	7135	.0478	19.73	.064	.338	
0 36	10975	.0509	19.71	.068	.336	
0 42	12886	.0473	19.75	.068	.344	
0 45	13538	.0509	19.76	.066	.340	
0 59	17978	.0555	19.78	.070	.326	
1 2	18670	.0498	19.71	.072	.346	
1 26	25808	.0528	20.06	.070	.334	
1 28	26460	.0492	19.85	.070	.344	
1 36	29065	.0522	19.62	.072	.344	
2 0	36069	.0563	19.41	.088	.366	
2 10	39232	.0594	19.00	.096	.374	
2 19	41844	.0631	18.60	.112	.402	
2 21	42476	.0669	18.14	.116	.410	
2 27	44373	.0701	18.80	.134	.436	
2 32	45704	.0744	17.25	.156	.468	
2 37	47102	.0810	16.65	.186	.510	
2 39	47811	.0847	16.16	.202	.534	
2 41	48485	.0893	15.78	.220	.560	
2 44	49214	.0942	15.36	.242	.588	
2 46	49957	.1017	14.69	.276	.636	
2 49	50715	.1121	13.95	.316	.698	
2 52	51651	.1348	12.77	.404	.812	
2 54	52472	.1596	11.69	.554	1.006	

Specimen failed at 53340 cycles after 2 hours 57 minutes

Figure 6 Computer output of dynamic mechanical data for a typical specimen

The maximum and minimum load (ie stress) were held constant by the test machine, while the maximum and minimum strain both increased as the specimen was cycled. The maximum strain increased at a greater rate than the minimum strain giving rise to a hysteresis loop of decreasing slope, and hence decreasing specimen stiffness throughout the test.

Both the modulus and damping data change in a similar progressive manner for the last 30,000 cycles. The modulus falls to 60% of its initial

value and the damping factor increases by more than 300%. In tests on other materials similar changes were recorded but the damping factor showed definite step changes in the increases.

Figure 7 Graphical output showing change in damping factor and storage modulus with cycles

In Figure 8 are shown the damping and modulus changes for four tests. The shorter life (higher stress) tests gave no incubation period and the initial values suggested damage had occurred in the initial loading sequence (ie modulus value lower, damping value higher than test 1). These different values may be associated with the mode of operation of the function generator on the fatigue machine which requires the mean load to be applied initially (0.55 x peak load) before the peak-to-peak amplitude is applied. So if the mean load is above the threshold for microcracking then damage occurs before the fatigue test actually starts. (NB: This disadvantage does not exist with machines that build up their waveforms from haversines as in the later computer controlled test machines.) The curves in Figure 8 have been extrapolated to the failure cycles from the last monitored data point. Later, and continuing, developments have reduced the data cycle time, currently 30 seconds, so that the specimen degradation is followed to a point closer to failure. Even allowing for this extrapolation there is a marked similarity in the curves in the post 'incubation' period of the test.

Figure 8 Change in storage modulus and damping factor with cycles at four stress levels (1=63 MN/m², 2=67.6 MN/m², 3=68.6 MN/m², 4=70 MN/m²)

Correlation between visual damage and dynamic mechanical data

The analysis used in (4) has been used in this work to relate the observed number of 45° cracks to the change in d and E' for the test prior to the final splitting damage. The hysteresis term $E'_D \Delta d$ is determined for each crack number observation and cross plotted in Figure 9. The data fit a straight line with an intercept at zero, in good agreement with the previous results for statically loaded specimens.

Once a system has been "calibrated" in this way, Figure 9 could be used to determine the state of damage from the monitored d and E' data. Further tests are, however, required over a wider range of stress levels to check that a single relationship exists.

Figure 9 Dependence of $E'_D \Delta d$ upon crack number for a $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate

CONCLUSIONS

Continuous monitoring of the specimen during fatigue testing using the dynamic mechanical analysis technique provides valuable information on the degradation of the specimen throughout the test. This additional information should increase the value of expensive fatigue tests. The technique could also be applied either continuously to actual components under service loads, or intermittently under service or proof load conditions.

The correlation tests described are the start of a series of investigations necessary to relate and validate recorded changes in DMA data with structural changes in the specimen. The trends observed to date suggest potential for predicting the final failure point, or in using the data directly for dynamic applications such as springs and flywheels, as well as in studies of failure mechanisms.

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